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A Review Article on Induction Training Program for the Teachers

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Abstract

A review article on Induction training program for the teachers was a new study. The following research questions were applied in this study: (1) Investigate induction training program for teachers in the literature review in Khyber Pakhtun Khwa. (2) To inquire the Induction training program for teachers in Punjab. (3) To explore the conclusion of Induction training program for teachers in Khyber Pakhtun Khwa and Punjab through literature. This study was delimited to the Induction training program for primary school teachers. A various number of research articles on Induction training program in KPK and in Punjab were search and critically analyzed. The purpose of this study was to analyze the Induction training program for teachers and its effects on teacher perdition after completing this program as well as to inquire KPK and Punjab induction training implementation and its process. It is concluded that mostly primary school teachers were in the favour of induction training program to improve the skills and enhance the competency. It is a nine-month training and during this period different subjects teach like class room management, Educational Psychology, ICT, English, Maths etc. Induction training is essential for improving teachers' abilities and knowledge so they can give their students a better-quality education.

Keywords: Teacher Induction, Professional Development, Training Program Effectiveness, New Teacher Support, Educational Capacity Building

INTRODUCTION

Induction program emphasis on enhancing classroom management skills, intended to support new teachers as they transition to a different career. The teacher's careless actions that could harm the pupils' educational process are not considered teaching. Setting instructional goals is influenced by the circumstances teachers face in the classroom, such as determining what abilities kids need to select pertinent learning

materials and plan suitable activities. Effective teaching requires thorough planning, according to the educationist, and this plan needs to be chosen before any classroom activities start. Shah, S. R., Ullah, H., and Irshad, A. (2025).

According to Avalos, 2016 the continuous process of improving and preserving a person's skills, knowledge, and experiences in their specific sector is referred to as "professional development." The term "continuous professional development" describes the work done to enhance, maintain, and expand one's current set of skills and information relevant to one's job. Professional development training can be as beneficial to management as it is to their employees.

Teachers need professional training to help children learn. Making this work fair and reasonable requires teaching, the noblest profession. Only by offering its population valid and efficient learning methods can a country progress. In great nations, education shapes society. Education fosters growth and stability. A great teacher "inspires," a good teacher "tells," an outstanding teacher "explains," and a superb teacher "demonstrates." In 2020, Akhtar et al.

Vaisanen and Sahito 2017 argues that teachers build countries. They assist pupils in becoming responsible individuals who have the ability to change the world. The Holy Prophet (SAW) emphasized the importance of teaching, which is regarded as a prophetic vocation in Islam. An exceptional teacher "explains," a great teacher "inspires," an excellent teacher "tells," and a wonderful teacher "demonstrates." Given that inexperienced teachers are more expensive and since teaching is a fulfilling career with many unanticipated challenges, it is imperative to invest in educators who can help children succeed. Like opera singers, teachers have to deal with creative problems. Both art and science are necessary for a quality education.

Methodologies, abilities, and practices are the main topics of teacher education. In-service training can be assessed using teaching and learning. Teachers of all grades can participate in competitions created to help their students succeed through professional development (PD) programs. The best teacher preparation programs place a strong emphasis on academic proficiency and give teachers practical experience while being supervised by an experienced mentor. Inadequate teacher preparation is a problem in Pakistan's educational system. Teachers can learn the newest subject matter, classroom management techniques, and teaching methodologies through in-service training Without a predetermined curriculum, teaching has no purpose and is a waste of time if innovative teaching techniques are not used (A. H. Khan & Aleem, 2014).

According to Khanam and Zulifiqar (2020) Developing supportive learning environments requires a deeper comprehension of child behavior asserts that teachers who took part in structured induction programs demonstrated better classroom management techniques and increased student achievement compared to those who did not. A deeper comprehension of child psychology and development is partly to blame for this progress. In their investigation into the effects of behavior management training during the induction phase, found that teachers who received focused instruction in behavior management techniques were more equipped to handle problems in the classroom, creating a more organized and effective learning environment.

According to Hassan (2024), teachers who took part in organized induction programs showed improved classroom management techniques and increased student achievement in comparison to those who did not. This progress can be partially ascribed to a deeper comprehension of child psychology and development.

INDUCTION PROGRAM IN PUNJAB

Teachers in Punjab get induction training at a specially created Academy for Educational Development. Training Needs Assessment (TNA) was the first stage of the induction training framework, according to academy's induction training framework. In any nation, but particularly in Pakistan, the education sector is crucial. This sector might be thought of as the grassland that the country of the future will walk on. In this sense, teachers are crucial because they assist mold young brains, foster intellectual development, and help pupils develop strong moral character. The launch of the Punjab Induction Training Program in 2009 is a notable illustration of this. Here, acknowledging the crucial responsibilities that educators perform in the educational network is highly valued (Parveen et al., 2022).

At the start of their professions, they develop important relationships with students and coworkers and learn skills that will empower, mentor, and inspire the next generation, according to Mabaso (2012). Nonetheless, this is the time to develop one's educational philosophy and professional identity. The creation of an ITP demonstrates how crucial it is to assisting, directing, and fostering teachers' professional development. In addition to offering teachers materials and organized training, an ITP empowers them to positively impact students' lives and the larger educational landscape. This crucial assistance is necessary because it empowers educators to address the issues confronting contemporary education and to actively engage in influencing the next generation (Mabaso, 2012).

In order to make sure that teachers receive the assistance, instruction, and materials they require to be successful in the classroom, the Punjab Teacher Education Task Force made this program mandatory for new teachers. In addition, the Department of Social Development organized a four-week professional development program to give them the necessary tools to support the region's desire for qualified, driven, and well-prepared educators who can provide high-quality instruction that benefits their students). In order to create a more educated and wealthy society, investing in teacher development enhances Punjab's educational system and raises the learning levels of its students Induction training is crucial for new instructors, according to Kearney (2010). In addition to improving student accomplishment and advancing teachers' expertise, it encourages teacher retention in the early stages of their careers (Abdullah et al., 2023).

According to Ingersoll and Strong (2011), who conducted research on teacher induction training programs, new teachers who participate in any kind of induction program perform better on a variety of teaching tasks, including creating lesson plans that are effective, keeping students on task, creating assignments that are tailored to the interests of the students, using effective student questioning strategies, exhibiting successful classroom management, and preserving a positive classroom environment. Additionally, their students score higher on achievement tests.

According to research, induction training programs influence how effective teachers are. "Teacher effectiveness is typically defined as emphasizing students' learning, the teacher's behavior, and the many methods they employ in the classroom. Better student results are also fostered by good teachers. Induction training continues to be a dynamic issue for every organization, and empirical research has given it a lot of attention. Since they have the power to create, maintain, and instruct the organizational culture, standards, regulations and its performance, etc., new hires must acquire new skills and teaching methods. Therefore, this means that enhancing or increasing the efficacy of induction-level training for new hires in a manner that helps them build the institution's valued resources (Campbell, 2017).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Islam places a strong importance on education, a powerful force that influences all aspect of a person's life. Numerous stakeholders have expressed disapproval of Pakistani teacher education due to its subpar quality and overly quantitative growth, it was stated. Since their teachers are not carrying out their professional responsibilities, students in public schools in developing countries like Pakistan are known to suffer (Anees, 2005).

According to Pasalari, Azizi, and Gholami (2022), in-service teacher education helps instructors improve by offering them planned, structured, and methodical coaching in a classroom setting.

People, especially youngsters, require in-service training to participate in society effectively. The skill, compassion, and motivation of a nation's educators determine the caliber of its citizens. According to Iqbal (1996), in-service teacher training must prioritize continuing education, setting an example, enhancing classroom instruction, and helping members develop their abilities, self-assurance, and independence. Administrators should encourage teachers' professional development and keep them updated on new findings and instructional strategies. The first step to a successful in-service program is collaboration.

Teachers plan how they may be more effective change agents and think about the ethical purpose of education as part of their professional development. Teachers gain the new information, practical skills, and emotional stability as well as IQ level required to plan, think, and interact professionally with pupil, teenagers, and co-workers (Kanwal, Nausheen, & Dilshad, 2019). asserts that in addition to its effectiveness, teacher preparation should be planned with the societal value system in mind. Religious values and beliefs must guide the planning and direction of teacher education. Programs for preparing teachers should make sure that they are morally pure, act in a way that complies with Shariah, and provide an example for their students.

In addition to teaching teachers how to teach, S.M. Shahid (2007) asserts that teacher education should help teachers develop their inherent abilities and potentialities so they can become more dynamic and capable of achieving successful teaching outcomes with the least amount of time, effort, and resources. Teacher education requires to be more dynamic. In order to develop highly educated, rational and scientifically oriented, uncompromising on quality, innovative, brave, and compassionate teachers who can keep up with society's technological change, the program of teacher education at all stages must be properly planned and constructed (Bennet, 2000).

Since teachers are so important to the growth of any community, their professional development has a profound impact on schools, students, and society at large. They are the change agents and play a variety of roles in the evolution of civilization. First, by helping their communities, they contribute to social transformation (Sofu, Thompson, & Kanton, 2019). Secondly, they are in charge of the quality of the educational system, which is primarily determined by the subject-matter expertise and professional credentials of the instructors. Instructors are crucial to the advancement of high-quality education, and effective instructors are crucial to the development of students' academic abilities and learning (Akinsolu, 2010; & Oluremi, 2013).

INDUCTION TRAINING PROGRAM IN PUNJAB

People can gain specialized skills and knowledge that they can use to their work through teacher training. These trainings assist teachers become more compatible, and their assessment aids in identifying circumstances that improve teachers' capacity to apply newly acquired knowledge and refine their instructional strategies. According to Holt (2012), instructors' effectiveness and work satisfaction are positively impacted by well-run induction programs. To assist new teachers, a teacher induction program provides a planned and structured curriculum.

Induction training programs are organized for a variety of reasons. Novice teachers transition into teaching with ease after completing induction training programs. It lowers the attrition rate among teachers and increases their ability to concentrate on high-quality instruction. New teachers can improve their teaching skills with the help of an induction program. It enables new educators to understand their unique teaching position (Loughry & Normore, 2013).

It was said by (Nandi, 2015) that Pakistan lacks the financial resources necessary to provide teacher training. Institutions, tools, equipment, audio-visual aids, books, and other reading materials are among the facilities that are lacking. An orientation and crucial step in helping instructors adjust to their work environment is induction. New hires are greeted to their workplace culture, co-workers, and their assignment during induction training. A component of teachers' ongoing professional development is the induction training program. It begins with pre-service training and lasts for a long time in a teacher's professional career. It addresses the range of professional requirements that educators have at every stage of their careers and future (Department of Education and Training, 2006).

According to Liakopoulou (2011), effective educators establish reasonable objectives, constantly inspire their pupil, employ a many of teaching techniques, favor participatory instruction, analysis and use their own instructional materials, clearly present information, use pictures and other teaching aids, try to inspire students to learn, apply a variety of teaching techniques, choose participatory teaching styles, test and create didactic material, present information in an understandable way, combine words and pictures, use a variety of teaching helping materials, make the most of their teaching time by organizing and minimizing disruptions in the classroom, assign activities that pique students' interest, track their progress based on predetermined standards, and provide feedback to their students.

Induction training is based on self-determination theory and self-efficacy theory. It defines self-efficacy as a person's confidence in his ability to accomplish desired outcomes. Induction training programs help teachers connect with their job and increase their self-efficacy (Pajares (1996).

According to the self-determination hypothesis, persons are inherently motivated to develop as human beings. Autonomy, relatedness, and competence are necessary for this demand, which is innate (Houde, 2006). Sweeny (2000) talked about three different types of teacher induction training programs. The basic orientation model (BOM) is the first model. The instruction practice model (IPM) is the second model. The school transformation model (STM) is the third model. His models serve as the foundation for the induction training programs that organizations create. Additionally, his models support the creation, execution, assessment, and upkeep of induction training initiatives.

The idea of teacher training has been proposed since the 19th century. Numerous studies have been conducted in this area. The studies have found that new teachers are better and more capable. The administration, parents, legislators, the business community, and society at large now hold teachers to extremely high standards. Only committed and skilled educators can live up to their expectations in this setting. Training institutions are in charge of monitoring training and technologies. Effective teaching and a thorough understanding of the subject matter are essential for improving student comprehension. Activities aimed at improving communication and establishing the new hire's comfort level inside the organization might be incorporated into the induction process. Brookhart (2011).

Effective educational practices have become more likely as information regarding teacher development and learning has advanced quickly. However, it entails combining several disciplines and connecting them to the understanding of successful teaching strategies that are emerging in the field of education (Darling-Hammond, Flook, Cook-Harvey, Barron & Osher, 2020).

The necessity of teacher training at all levels has increased as the world deals with training in practically every area of life. Transferring skills, information, and attitude to instructors is the aim of the program. Training has a significant impact on teachers, giving them the assurance that the department is actively supporting their transition to a new position. The organization also benefits from the new teacher's accomplishment. Additionally, induction-level training assists new hires in minimizing the challenges they face when they first begin their careers. After they solve their challenges, they begin to contribute in the most effective manner to achieve the organization's goals and objectives (Antonacopoulou & Guttel, 2010).

According to Wonacott (2002), Wonacott asserts that induction programs assist educators in developing their abilities, efficacy, and output. No one should underestimate the importance of early professional development by enlisting the help of seasoned teachers and school officials. Two other essential components are (a) ongoing individual assistance, evaluation, and feedback, and (b) further education, which is developed on professional education. According to Noe and Kodwani (2008), the training and learning process is concerned with the components utilized for the program in order to increase the likelihood that it will be able to transmit knowledge at a higher level. Characterizing, identifying, targeting, and extension are all handled by the training

design in order to communicate the training plan and its goals. The induction training's objective is determined by the training needs analysis process, which covers the necessary tasks.

According to Pahuja (2015), there is a lot of discussion on the start-up and commencement of the training and process of development. The training facilities must attest that the instructors and students have disclosed and are ready to communicate and adjust on their own. The training program should start at the designated time. Resources that are available for use include money, cars, supportive mentors, and assistance. Facilities including classrooms, support structures, furniture, and the overall state of the physical environment should all be beneficial to learning. Referring to the phases or procedures involved in an induction training process ensures that the anticipated results can be realized. The induction training procedure consists of four parts. a) Training needs analysis, b) Training design, training use, and training monitoring and assessment

Training programs for teachers are conducted both before and during work so that they may use technology and proper approaches and help create new knowledge. By promoting the use of deep learning (Noah & Olusola, 2015), teacher preparation improves students' cognitive learning strategies and, eventually, their academic performance (Schroeder et al., 2015).

CONCLUSION

According to this study, newly hired primary school teachers' professional development is significantly and favourably impacted by the induction training program conducted by Khyber Pakhtunkhwa's Directorate of Professional Development (DPD). Lesson planning skills, classroom management abilities, and knowledge of child psychology are among the fundamental teaching competencies that are successfully improved by the curriculum. These skills taken together help teachers perform better overall. The current study's findings demonstrate how organised induction training can significantly improve educational outcomes at the primary school level by providing new instructor the skills and information they required to establish productive learning environments. Mostly primary school teachers were of the opinion that induction training program is playing a crucial role for the improvement of teachers and have a positive effects on performance. After completion of induction training program mostly teachers used different strategies in the class, plan activities before class and learn how to make difficult topic easy and intractable, how to manage the skills how to utilize minimum resources to make activity-based learning, increased students' creativity.

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